

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MODERN COMPUTER OPERATING SYSTEMS AND THEIR CONVENIENCE

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Аннотация. Эта статья поможет вам управлять связью между компьютерами и пользователями, управлять ресурсами и выполнять другие задачи, которые должны выполнять компьютеры.

Abstract. This article helps you manages, and perform other tasks that computers need to perform.

Ключевые слова. Операционные системы, яркость и корректная работа, управление и интерфейс, безопасность, шифрование данных, исправление ошибок, эффективное управление памятью.

Keywords. Operating systems, brightness and correct performance, management and interface, security, data encryption, error correction, effective memory management.

Modern operating systems (OS) are the main programs that run a computer differently from other programs. Their main tasks are to manage computer devices, organize communication with users, manage resources and perform other tasks that a computer should perform.

Modern operating systems ensure brightness and correct operation. Based on their optimized code and procedure manuals, users can easily launch programs, access and exit them, manage files and folders, change system settings, and perform other basic tasks.

Modern operating systems offer user-friendly management interfaces. These interfaces are easy to use and do not require much training or technical knowledge. Graphical interfaces, related to menus and commands, changes and settings, provide a meaningful and vivid experience for users.

Modern operating systems pay great attention to the security of user data and systems. Their security protocols, authentication methods, data encryption, file and system-to-system security analysis and guides help users stay secure.

Modern operating systems help facilitate connectivity and integration with networks, devices, and other applications. Their related protocols and interfaces work easily to receive data from other systems, refer to them, and exchange information with them.

Modern operating systems provide opportunities for updating and rounding up to meet the demands and requests of their customers. These updates may typically include new versions of written software, offering full downloads and services, bug fixes, highly simplified setup, easier modifications, launch, and manuals.

All these conveniences increase brightness and efficiency for users through the modern operating system of the computer and help to manage the computer processes well.

The difference between modern computer operating systems may be in the possibilities they provide to users and the principles of system operation. Let's take a look at some of the differences between modern operating systems below:

The Windows operating system is produced by Microsoft. It is one of the most common and widely used operating systems. Among Windows, there are versions like Windows 10, Windows 8, Windows 7, Windows Vista, Windows XP. Windows system is generally characterized by security, simplicity, graphical interface and multitasking. It has a unique user interface (Start menu, Taskbar, Windows Explorer) that provides easy and meaningful operation for users.

There are programs and games that are common among Windows. It has a simple interface and is easy to use. The Windows system provides multitasking and allows collaboration with several devices.

There may be security issues for some users. Its license is expensive and may require additional payment for updates.

The MacOS operating system is produced by Apple and can only be installed on Apple computers. macOS is characterized by an easy interface, related systems and various features. Its next versions will consist of (Catalina, Mojave, High Sierra, Sierra).

MacOS stands out for its intuitive interface and ease of use. It integrates well with Apple systems and allows users to work easily and efficiently. In its updates, users are usually offered to make changes easier and offer new features.

MacOS only works on computers made by Apple and has limited usability on other computers. There are many different versions of the Linux operating system, such as Ubuntu, Fedora, Debian, CentOS, Arch Linux, etc. A Linux system has its own layout and interfaces, and usually provides a wide range of features and customization options. Among Linux, there are also open source systems that allow you to modify and use the code of all systems.

Chrome OS is an operating system developed by Google and commonly used on computers called Chromebooks. This system is usually used in internet-dependent devices and is mainly launched through the web browser Chrome. Chrome OS is the easiest, most secure, and features automatic updates to update itself.

The fact that each modern operating system has its own advantages and limitations is important in providing the necessary opportunities for users. Users are advised to choose an operating system that works best with their system requirements and personal needs.

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